

Procedure for monitoring and control of health and quality risks

NTNU, *Rizza Ardiyanti and Cynthia Hallé*

SINTEF, *Kamal Azrague*

October-2021

Achieving wider uptake of water-sm art solutions

Project number: 869283

Project duration: May 2020 – April 2024

H2020-SC5-2019-2

WWW.WIDER-UPTAKE.EU

D2.1 – Public

Procedure for monitoring and control of health and quality risks

VERSION

03

DATE

30-October-2021

ABSTRACT

This document presents a general framework for monitoring and controlling health and quality risks that can account for the multi-actor contributions to the risks in symbiotic relations between water utilities and industries in a circular economy context. The framework is based on three pillar evaluations for ensuring that the recovered wastewater products have high quality, minimum health, and environmental risks. To account for the multi-actor contributions, the scope in the quality assessment is divided into two categories. The wastewater utility is responsible for the recovered resources from the wastewater plant. The industry as the next actor is responsible for the quality for the final products. To ensure the comprehensiveness of the monitoring plan, the important elements for monitoring specifically monitoring parameters, monitoring frequency and monitoring locations are developed based on problem formulation principles in QMRA and QCRA methods.

KEYWORDS

Resource recovery, risk assessment, health risk, environmental risk, contaminant of emerging concern, pathogen, water reuse, struvite, fertiliser, soil improver, biochar, biopolymer, biocomposite, biogas, energy

DELIVERABLE ID

D2.1

WORK PACKAGE

WP2

PLANNED DELIVERY DATE

31-October-2021

AUTHORSHIP AND APPROVAL INFORMATION

LEAD BENEFICIARY
NTNU

AUTHOR(S)
Rizza Ardiyanti (NTNU)
Cynthia Hallé (NTNU)
Kamal Azrague (SINTEF)

REVIEWED BY
Thomas Meyn (NTNU)
Gema Raspati (SINTEF)

RELEASE HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	VERSION DESCRIPTION/MILESTONE*	DESCRIPTION
01	22-October-2021	Internal review	
02	29-October-2021	Delivered for final check	
03	30-October-2021	Final version	

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	6
1 INTRODUCTION.....	7
1.1 Background.....	7
1.2 Objectives.....	7
1.3 Structure of Report.....	8
2 LEGISLATIVE BACKGROUND.....	9
2.1 Introduction.....	9
3 GENERAL MONITORING FRAMEWORK.....	12
3.1 Quality and compliance.....	15
3.2 Human health protection.....	20
3.3 Environmental protection.....	23
4 ASSESSMENT METHODS FOR QUALITY AND RISK ANALYSIS.....	27
4.1 Product quality assessment.....	27
4.2 Risk assessment.....	27
4.2.1 Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment.....	28
4.2.2 Quantitative Chemical Risk Assessment.....	32
4.2.3 Databases.....	39
5 REFERENCES.....	40
APPENDIX I: EXAMPLE OF MONITORING PLAN.....	43

LIST OF FIGURES

<i>Figure 1: General framework for wastewater recovered product assessment</i>	12
<i>Figure 2: Recovered resources and associated final products</i>	15
<i>Figure 3: Division between CMCs and PFCs in EU Fertilising Products Regulations</i>	16
<i>Figure 4: Flow scheme for establishing monitoring plan for quality compliance</i>	17
<i>Figure 5: Flow scheme for establishing monitoring plan for health protection</i>	21
<i>Figure 6: Main steps in health risk assessment</i>	22
<i>Figure 7: Flow scheme for establishing monitoring plan for environmental protection</i>	24
<i>Figure 8: Main steps in environmental risk assessment</i>	25
<i>Figure 9: Exposure pathways for fertilizers risk assessment (Kraus & Seis, 2015)</i>	26

LIST OF TABLES

<i>Table 1: EU legislative background</i>	10
<i>Table 2: Overview of relevant regulations and reference product specifications</i>	18
<i>Table 3: Different concepts of health-based doses</i>	34

GLOSSARY

ADI	: Allowable Daily Intake
CEC	: Contaminant of Emerging Concern
CHP	: Combined Heat and Power
CMC	: Component Material Category
DALY	: Disability adjusted life years
DM	: Dry Matter
DWTP	: Drinking Water Treatment Plant
ECHA	: European Chemical Agency
EFSA	: European Food Safety Authority
EGD	: European Green Deal
EQS	: Environmental Quality Standard
LCA	: Life Cycle Assessment
PEC	: Predicted Environmental Concentration
PFC	: Product Function Category
PNEC	: Predicted No-Effect Concentration
POP	: Persistent Organic Pollutant
ppyi	: per person per year
QMRA	: Quantitative microbial risk assessment
QCRA	: Quantitative chemical risk assessment
RCR	: Risk Characterization Ratio
REACH	: Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
SDG	: Sustainable Development Goals
TDI	: Tolerable Daily Intake
US-EPA	: United State-Environmental Protection Agency
WRRF	: Water Resource Recovery Facility
WWTP	: Wastewater treatment plant

Executive summary

Wider Uptake is built around a set of innovative circular economy solutions co-developed by water utilities and private businesses from industry sectors. Closing the material loops contributes towards sustainable development but may also present risks to human health and the environment.

Hence, a general monitoring framework has been developed and will be demonstrated in the Wider Uptake project. The framework provides a guideline in establishing a monitoring plan that allows a thorough evaluation of the recovered resources and their associated final products. The framework is based on 3 pillars. Pillar-1 ensures product quality and compliance, Pillar-2 confirms safety to human health, and Pillar-3 certifies safety to the environment.

Quality assessment of recovered resources and associated final products is based on relevant laws (e.g., REACH, CEC watch list, Drinking water directive, POP regulation, etc). Innovative products may not yet be regulated therefore a set of indicators must be determined by product users based on the presence of potential substances.

Human health risks will be based on the EU regulations, and existing standards for microbiological and chemical parameters. Monitoring plans in different contexts (e.g., wastewater reuse, nutrient recovery, materials recovery, etc.) will be developed. The choice of parameters to be monitored will be coordinated to achieve a coherent set of data with measurable indicators for quality and health in Wider Uptake. Preservation of the environment is also a criterion for the transition to water-smart solutions. Waste recovery should be produced and used without the addition of environmental pressure. In the framework, quality of products, human health risks and environmental risks are based on quantitative microbial risks assessment (QMRA) and chemical risk assessment (QCRA). Using quantitative assessment of risk, a safe circular economy can be developed by identifying and applying mitigation of risk factors.

This report is organised into four chapters. The first chapter sets the background information, objectives and introduces the structure of the report. The second chapter discusses the legislative background for identifying critical parameters that are important for the wastewater recovered products according to the EU standards. The third chapter of this report presents the developed general monitoring framework and the 3-pillar evaluations for ensuring the product quality, health, and environmental protection. The last section, Chapter 4, describes the assessment methods that are used in the evaluation of product quality, health risks and environmental risks.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Water scarcity, population growth and pollution of water resources are major challenges for achieving the water related United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Despite the urgent need to secure natural water resources, the implementation of water-smart solutions is limited. Therefore, facilitating the transition from waste facility to resource recovery facility is a major goal in Wider Uptake.

Wider Uptake is built around a set of innovative circular economy solutions co-developed by water utilities and private businesses from industry sectors with high water consumption, high use of material resources and energy-agriculture industry, building & manufacturing materials industry, and energy supply. Besides the technological demonstration studies, the project also demonstrates measures for wider implementation of recovered resources through activities on monitoring and control of health and quality risks, assessing circular-economy and efficiency potential, developing business models for industrial symbiosis, and measuring water smartness and progress towards Sustainable Development Goal.

In circular economy, it is necessary for recovered waste to be recycled or reuse in final products using water-smart solution. Closing the material loops contributes towards sustainable development but may also present risks to human health and the environment. The inherent risk from the wide range of contaminants in wastewater, as one of the main barriers for the widespread implementation of the recovered products, will be addressed in this report.

1.2 Objectives

The objective of this report is to present the general monitoring framework in the Wider Uptake project. The framework is developed to provide a guideline in establishing a monitoring plan that allows a thorough evaluation of the recovered resources and their associated final products. The framework is based on 3 pillars. Pillar-1 ensures product quality and compliance, Pillar-2 confirms safety to human health, and Pillar-3 certifies safety to the environment.

Quality assessment of recovered resources and associated products is based on relevant laws (e.g., REACH, CEC watch list, Drinking water directive, POP regulation, etc). Innovative products may not yet be regulated therefore a set of indicators must be determined by products users based on the presence of potential substances.

Human health risks will be based on the EU regulations, and existing standards for microbiological and chemical parameters. Monitoring plans in different contexts (e.g., wastewater reuse, nutrient recovery, materials recovery, etc.) will be developed. The choice of parameters to be monitored will be coordinated to achieve a coherent set of data with measurable indicators for quality and health in Wider Uptake. Preservation of the environment is also a criterion for the transition to water-smart solutions. Waste recovery should be produced and used without the addition of environmental pressure. In the framework, quality of products, human health risks and environmental risks are based on quantitative microbial risks assessment (QMRA) and chemical risk assessment (QCRA).

Using quantitative assessment of risk, a safe circular economy can be developed by identifying and applying mitigation of risk factors.

By applying a transparent and systematic approach, Wider Uptake will demonstrate the quality of products obtained from recovered resources, establishing human health and environmental protection. The framework will help decision makers and stakeholders to promote the use of innovative products and balance the effort required to control risks associated with exposure to substances of concerns.

1.3 Structure of Report

This report is organised into four chapters. The first chapter sets the background information, objectives and introduces the structure of the report. The second chapter discusses the legislative background for identifying critical parameters that are important for the wastewater recovered products according to the EU standards. The third chapter of this report presents the developed general monitoring framework and the 3-pillar evaluations for ensuring the product quality, health, and environmental protection. The last section, Chapter 4, describes the assessment methods that are used in the evaluation of product quality, health risks and environmental risks.

2 Legislative background

2.1 Introduction

The European Green Deal (EGD) establishes the objective of becoming climate neutral in 2050 in a manner that contributes to the European economy, growth, and jobs. There are already established directives that facilitate the EGD strategy such as the Water Framework Directive¹ and Waste Framework Directive² which lay down the basic concepts of an integrated water and waste management that promote recycling and recovery of non-hazardous waste (European Commission, 2000, 2008, 2018b). The EU regulations that set a benchmark for wastewater recovered products are currently limited to Regulation (EU) 2020/741 Minimum requirement for water reuse and Regulation (EU) No. 2019/1009 for EU fertilising products.

There is currently no EU-wide legislative framework to support the use of renewable raw materials, nor an EU law in place applicable to bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics in a comprehensive manner (DG Environment, 2021; European Bioplastics e.V., 2016). The European Committee for Standardization (CEN) has published several standards on bio-based products, but there is no clarity concerning plastic products that are entirely or partly derived from biomass (DG Environment, 2021). The other important directive that is currently under revision is the Renewable Energy Directive II³ (European Commission, 2018a). The final proposal for amending the current Renewable Energy Directive was published in July 2021 and is currently in the public consultation stage (European Biogas Association, 2021; European Commission, 2021).

The study of EU legislative background begins from the EU regulations directly related to water reuse and resource recovery, including relevant regulations under the Water Framework Directive and the Waste Framework directive. The objective of the legislative background study is to gather together the existing EU regulations that can be used for the identification of critical parameters that are important for the wastewater recovered products. Summary of EU legislative background for the development of general monitoring framework for ensuring product quality, human health protection and the environment protection is outlined in Table 1.

In Wider Uptake, a wide range of innovative products recovered from wastewater are evaluated. Some products such as reclaimed water, struvite and soil improver are already regulated. However, for innovative and intermediate products, such as recovered cellulose for biocomposite and Polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA), a dedicated regulation is not yet in place. In Wider Uptake demo studies, new innovative products that are currently not regulated are nutrient-embedded biochar, biogas, biochar fuel, recovered cellulose and PHA. A quality evaluation protocol is proposed by referring to a similar regulation or by using a set of parameters that are commonly used for similar conventional products.

For instance, nutrient-embedded biochar for intended use as slow-release fertilisers is not explicitly listed in the Regulation (EU) No. 2019/1009. However, a similar approach applied in Regulation (EU) No. 2019/1009 can be implemented. The assessment of nutrient-embedded biochar is categorised into Component Material Category (CMC) and Product Function

¹Water Framework Directive - Directive 2000/60/EC

²Waste Framework Directive - Directive (EU) 2018/851

³Renewable Energy Directive II- Directive (EU) 2018/2001

Category (PFC). Therefore, the parameters used for product quality monitoring shall adhere to both the European Biochar Certification and the Directive 91/271/EEC concerning urban wastewater treatment, since the feedstock is biochar, and the embedded nutrients are recovered from the WWTP effluent. At last, the Regulation (EU) No. 2019/1009 is also applied since the intended product application is as fertilizer.

Table 1: EU legislative background

EU legislation	Description	Relevant information for monitoring plan
Regulation (EU) 2020/741	Minimum requirement for water reuse	Quality specifications of water reuse for different applications
Regulation (EU) 2019/1009	EU fertilising products	Quality specifications of wastewater recovered resources and the associated fertiliser products
Directive 2000/60/EC	Water Framework Directive	Provide guidance in identifying a set of regulations for pollution prevention in water bodies, provide policy framework for the integrated water basin managements.
Directive (EU) 2018/851	Waste Framework Directive	Provide guidance in the implementation of waste hierarchy and waste valorisation concepts
Directive (EU) 2018/2001	Renewable Energy Directive II	Quality specifications and sustainability criteria for bioenergy, provide information on default values of greenhouse gas emissions and typical fuel energy content
Directive 91/271/EEC	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive	Quality specifications of urban WWTP effluent
Directive 86/278/EEC	Sewage Sludge Directive	Quality specifications of sewage sludge to be used in agriculture
Directive 2006/118/EC	Ground Water Directive	Environmental protection. The directive provides a list of parameters and indicators for groundwater monitoring.
Directive 91/676/EEC	Nitrates Directive	Quality specifications of nitrates concentration in freshwater bodies and codes of good agricultural practice.
Directive 2013/39/EU	(revised) Environmental Quality Standards Directive, EQS Directive	Environmental protection: provide information about priority substances in the field of water policy,
Decision (EU) 2020/1161	Recent watch-list of emerging pollutants and substances	Environmental protection: provide information about priority substances in the field of water policy
Directive (EU) 2020/2184	(revised) Drinking Water Directive	Health protection: to estimate tolerable health-based values when TDI data are not available

Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006	REACH Regulation	Protection of human health and the environment from the risks posed by chemicals
Regulation (EU) 2019/1021	POPs Regulation	Protection of human health and the environment from the risks of persistent organic pollutants
Regulation (EC) No 178/2002	EU food safety policy	Provide guidance in food safety and hygiene. Protection of human health from the risk of trace chemicals and microbial contaminants in food products, such as safe and effective use of fertiliser products and pesticides.

Source: European Commission, 2021

For the remaining unregulated innovative products, the attainable targeted product quality will be reported and compared with similar commercial products. Baseline studies will also be used to gather information about the quality. The attainable product quality data from the Wider Uptake pilot study can be used to propose a realistic harmonized standard for these innovative products.

It is important to take into account that the major revision in the EU directives and regulations is mainly set in order to facilitate the EU Green Deal strategy and the circular economy transition (European Commission, 2021). The recent EU regulations already ratified or under revision, represent only the basic requirements. A set of regulated parameters might not adequately provide necessary protections towards human health and the environment. Hence, in addition to adhering to these regulations, the responsible actors are encouraged to consider more aspects and to look beyond the regulations.

3 General monitoring framework

The inherent risk from the wide range of contaminants in wastewater is one of the main barriers to the widespread implementation of recovered products. The general monitoring framework in the Wider Uptake is developed to address these concerns. The framework will provide a guideline for establishing a monitoring plan that allows a comprehensive evaluation of recovered resources and associated final products.

As outlined in Figure 1, the framework captures the three key concerns in wastewater recovered products specifically product quality, human health and environmental protection (Kehrein et al., 2020; RIVM, 2019). The framework aims to provide assurance that the established monitoring plan generates adequate data for the 3-pillar evaluations of recovered resources and resulting products. Each evaluation pillar provides a specific protection: access to a high-quality product for the consumers (Pillar-1), minimum impact on human health (Pillar-2) and minimum impact on the environment (Pillar-3).

Figure 1: General framework for wastewater recovered product assessment

The key indicators for each pillar evaluation are elaborated below:

1. Product quality and compliance (Pillar-1)
Key indicator of Pillar-1: the recovered raw materials and their associated final products fulfil the quality requirements set out by regulations or by market demands.
2. Human health protection (Pillar-2)
Key indicator of Pillar-2: the microbial risk is below the WHO health-based target which is 10^{-6} DALY per person per year (pppy)⁴ (WHO, 2016) and the chemical Risk Characterisation Ratio (RCR) is below 1 (ECHA, 2016a).

⁴ To give a better understanding, 10^{-6} DALY or 1 μ DALY pppy represents an equivalent disease burden associated with mild diarrhea at an annual disease risk of approximately one watery diarrhea in 1000 persons per year (WHO & UNEP, 2006b).

For the microbial risk, DALYs (Disability Adjusted Life Years) metric is chosen because different health outcomes can be compared using this metric. DALYs attempt to measure the time lost because of disability or mortality from a disease compared with a long life free of disability in the absence of disease.

3. Environmental protection (Pillar-3)

Key indicator of Pillar-3: The environmental risk characterisation ratio is below 1 (ECHA, 2016a).

In this project, risk evaluation will be performed based on QMRA and QCRA methods. Product quality assessment will be based on target comparison. QMRA and QCRA are chosen for the evaluation methods because the methods explicitly address and quantify the risk related to microbial and chemical hazards (ECHA, 2016a; WHO, 2016). These methods are also increasingly being applied by international agencies and governments as the basis for setting of health based-performance targets.

The important elements in developing a monitoring plan are to have a correct set of monitoring parameters, well-defined sampling location and sampling frequency. Knowing which regulations, reference products and risk assessment methods to be used is the starting point in developing the framework.

Monitoring parameters

Defining a set of monitoring parameters in the quality assessment is relatively straightforward. For this purpose, the available regulations, or the specifications from similar reference products in the market can be used. For defining the monitoring parameters for controlling human health and environmental risks, the parameters can be based on the results from the hazard identification step.

Hazard identification step is adopted from the general risk assessment methods (WHO, 2010, 2016). Hazard identification is normally also referred to as problem formulation. In this step, hazards and their exposure scenarios are identified. Hazards in this report include microbial pathogens and chemicals that can potentially harm human and the environment. Whereas exposure scenarios are a combination of facts, assumptions, and inferences that define a situation where potential exposures may occur (WHO/IPCS, 2004). These may include the source, exposure routes or pathways, exposed population groups, exposure frequency, time frame and activities.

Monitoring locations

The monitoring of quality is directly performed on the recovered products: recovered resources and final products. On the other hand, the determination of sampling locations for controlling health and environmental risks can be more complex. Sampling locations for the purpose of controlling those risks will depend on the considered exposure scenarios, where the affected systems and the affected environmental compartments are defined.

In the case where surface water is one of the affected environmental compartments considered in the assessment, the adjacent water bodies need to be included as monitoring locations. If the affected systems include the distribution line due to the risk of pathogens regrowth, consequently the distribution line is to be included in the list of monitoring locations.

Monitoring frequency

When the wastewater recovered products are regulated, the monitoring frequency can simply be based on those specific regulations. If the product is not regulated, the monitoring frequency can be defined as such that the collected data are adequate to perform a reliable analysis. In addition, depending on the considered exposure scenarios for example in a case of increased chemical leaching from fertilizer in rainy periods, the monitoring frequency shall also be adjusted according to the relevant hazardous events in this case the seasonal variation.

The last step is to ensure that sampling and measurements are performed according to standards. The information about the standardized analysis methods for liquid samples and solid/sediment samples can be based on the official EU technical documents or EU regulations such as in the Directive (EU) 2020/2184: EU (revised) Drinking Water Directive, Annex II & III, or in JRC Technical Proposal (Huygens et al., 2019) for Fertilising Products Regulation chapter 5.7.

Quality management

In Section 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3 the flow schemes guiding the development of a monitoring plan are provided to ensure that the required set of measured parameters can enable the resource recovery actors:

- (A) to decide when the control measure/intervention is needed and
- (B) to assess the recovered resources and the final products performance

The general monitoring framework includes options for control measures when the product quality does not comply with the specifications or when the risk of the product implementation is above the risk indicator. The options are indicated by the dashed-lined loop coming back to the WWTP/WRRF and the Production Facility. These control measures can be in the form of:

1. Improvement of the recovery and/or production process
2. Risk control onsite

The challenge of defining the monitoring reference values for risk control

In implementing a monitoring activity, it is crucial to know when an intervention or a control measure is needed. In order to do so, a target value as a monitoring reference is needed. Thus, a control measure can be introduced immediately. For quality and compliance, if the specific product is regulated, one can simply refer to these numbers. In a case of a new innovative product, this value can be derived from the highest reasonable attained target during the experiment. It can be a target number for purity or a maximum limit for organic pollutants.

For risk control related to human health and environmental risk, the reference value for monitoring can be derived or refined from inverse risk calculation. When the acceptable risk level is known, in this case is when microbial pathogen risk below 10^{-6} DALY pppy and Risk Characterization Ratio (RCR) for chemical-related risk is below 1, the reference target value that can be used for monitoring can be obtained from the inverse risk calculation (WHO, 2016). In this case, the risk assessment can be performed only when a new or recommissioned plant is put into operation, or during a periodic risk assessment. For regular monitoring, one can refer to the reference value derived from the inverse risk calculation to determine when the intervention or a risk control measure is required.

3.1 Quality and compliance

The assessment entails the evaluation of recovered product quality and fulfilment of the current EU regulations. Pillar-1 represents the first evaluation point for determining whether the product can enter the market. The evaluation results can demonstrate if a new product has a market value and can offer the same quality as similar conventional products in the market.

In evaluating the product quality, the scope is divided based on two identified actors and two main products:

1. The first actor is the Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP)/Water Resource Recovery Facility (WRRF). Their product will be secondary raw materials, defined as the recovered resources in this report.
2. The second actor is the production facility. Their product is produced using one or more of the recovered wastes and referred to as final product in this report. The main activity in a production facility involves adjusting the final product composition. These can include, but are not limited to, blending, moulding, or polishing.

In some cases, WWTP utility and production facility can be the same entity. For example, in most cases for water reuse the WWTP operator is also responsible for the operational of the production facility.

<u>RECOVERED RESOURCES</u>		<u>FINAL PRODUCTS</u>
<i>Water Recovery</i>		
WWTP effluent	→	Reclaimed water for Agriculture
WWTP effluent	→	Reclaimed water for Park irrigation
<i>Fertilizer Recovery</i>		
WWTP (dewatered) digestate	→	Soil improver
WWTP (reject-water) digestate	→	Organo-mineral fertilizer
WWTP effluent	→	Nutrient-embedded biochar
<i>Energy Recovery</i>		
WWTP biogas	→	Heat & electricity, Biogas fuel
WWTP (dewatered) sludge	→	Char-briquettes
<i>Specific Product Recovery</i>		
WWTP recovered cellulose, and DWTP recovered lime pellets	→	Bio-composite
WWTP recovered PHA	→	PHA biopolymer pellets

Figure 2: Recovered resources and associated final products

Dividing the assessment scope between the recovered resource and the final product will make the regulation identifying process less complex. Using this approach, each actor contributions to risks can also easily be identified. The list of recovered resources and the

associated final products being demonstrated in the Wider Uptake project are outlined in Figure 2.

To facilitate the assessment, a division between the recovered resources and the final product is used, adopting the same approach as the Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 for EU Fertilising Products by Huygens et al., (2019).

Example

One of the demonstration cases in Norway produces soil improver and struvite fertilizer products. In this case, the relevant regulation is the EU Fertilising Products Regulation (EU) 2019/1009. The latter includes provisions for EU fertilising products that contain requirements at two levels, according to their intended function (Product Function Category, PFC), and according to their underlying component materials (Component Material Categories, CMC) as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Division between CMCs and PFCs in EU Fertilising Products Regulations (European Commission, 2019; Huygens et al., 2019)

According to the Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, for soil improver, the compliance applies for both IVAR, representing the WWTP/WRRF role, and HØST, representing the production facility/fertiliser factory. IVAR compliance is regulated under CMC 5 and HØST compliance is regulated under PFC 3A, organic (biopellets) soil improver.

For the struvite fertiliser pilot study, HIASIKS (together with HIASHow2O, Enwa and Sirkula) will act as both WWTP/WRRF and production facility/ fertilizer factory. They will be responsible for both nutrient recovery and adjusting the final fertilizer product composition. Their compliance is regulated both under CMC 5 and PFC 1B(I), solid organo-mineral fertiliser.

The flow scheme to establish a monitoring plan for quality assessment of recovered resource and final product is outlined in Figure 4.

RECOVERED RESOURCE

FINAL PRODUCT

Figure 4: Flow scheme for establishing monitoring plan for quality compliance

The flow scheme for product quality compliance is based on the individual evaluation of each actor's product. In the product quality assessment, the evaluation is performed by comparing the composition of the recovered products with the EU regulations or similar conventional products in the market. The required data for product quality assessment is the measured product composition. The products are shown to have a market value and can be marketed when the quality specifications are fulfilled. Otherwise, there should be an improvement in the recovery and/or production process. Another option is to consider a different application for the recovered product that requires lower quality specifications.

In addition to using the apparent regulations such as the minimum requirement for water reuse and the EU fertilising products, for the recovered resources other regulations like the Urban wastewater treatment directive and the Sewage sludge directive can also be used. These regulations can be used because the components exiting WWTP are effluent water and sewage sludge. Moreover, these components are not leaving WWTP as the final products but as secondary raw materials.

To develop the plan for monitoring of product quality in the Wider Uptake case studies, the regulations and reference product specifications listed in Table 2 can be used as a starting point.

Table 2: Overview of relevant regulations and reference product specifications

Recovery classification	Relevant regulations and reference product specifications	
	Recovered resource	Final product
Water recovery	<u>Effluent water</u> Directive 91/271/EEC, Urban wastewater treatment directive	<u>Reclaimed water</u> Regulation (EU) 2020/741, Minimum requirement for water reuse
Fertiliser recovery	<u>(Reject-water) digestate</u> CMC quality requirements under Regulation (EU) No. 2019/1009, EU fertilising products	<u>Struvite-based fertilisers</u> PFC quality requirements under Regulation (EU) No. 2019/1009, EU fertilising products
	<u>(Dewatered) digestate</u> CMC quality requirements under Regulation (EU) No. 2019/1009, EU fertilising products	<u>Biopellet soil improvers</u> PFC quality requirements under Regulation (EU) No. 2019/1009, EU fertilising products
	<u>Effluent water</u> 1. Directive 91/271/EEC, Urban wastewater treatment directive	<u>Nutrient-embedded biochar</u> 1. PFC quality requirements under Regulation (EU) No. 2019/1009, EU fertilising products 2. European Biochar Certificate (European Biochar Foundation (EBC), 2016)

Energy recovery	<p><u><i>(Dewatered) sewage sludge</i></u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Directive 86/278/EEC, Sewage Sludge Directive 2. CMC quality requirements under Regulation (EU) No. 2019/1009, (for comparison) 	<p><u><i>Biochar fuel (briquettes)</i></u></p> <p>Reference thermal properties (calorific value, burning rate, CO₂ emission, ash content, etc.) of similar products such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marketed briquettes from WASH Sanitation project - Conventional marketed charcoal
	<p><u><i>Biogas</i></u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Renewable Energy Directive - Directive (EU) 2018/2001 	<p><u><i>Heat and Electricity</i></u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maximum limit values for CO₂ and H₂S from CHP unit specifications 2. Typical methane content and calorific values 3. Renewable Energy Directive - Directive (EU) 2018/2001
		<p><u><i>Biogas fuel</i></u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Quality specifications from local injection gas grid 2. Renewable Energy Directive - Directive (EU) 2018/2001
Intermediate-product recovery	<p><u><i>Recovered cellulose</i></u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reference composition of recycled waste-cellulose e.g., Recell® cellulose 2. Typical pathogens and heavy metals composition in primary sludge. 	<p><u><i>Biocomposite material</i></u></p> <p>Reference composition of biocomposite specifications, according to the intended application: Canal bank protection</p>
	<p><u><i>Recovered lime pellets</i></u></p> <p>Reference composition of lime pellets e.g., from AquaMinerals BV</p>	
	<p><u><i>Recovered PHA</i></u></p> <p>Reference composition of PHA composition from residual waste mix culture</p>	

Recovery classifications from Kehrein et al., (2020) were selected to describe the wastewater recovered product categories. The term ‘Intermediate-product recovery’ is chosen because the process is often related to the provision of intermediate products instead of the final products consumed by end-users. Hence, the typical supply chain may involve more actors. Intermediate-product recoveries within the Wider Uptake project comprise PHA and cellulose. However, in a bigger scope the intermediate product recovery can include the recovery of specific metals, biochemicals such as extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) and volatile fatty acid (VFA), and other N&P non-fertiliser products.

Defining the reference values for monitoring of the intermediate products will depend on case by case. Currently it is not easily standardized because the consumers of the intermediate products are often industries. If PHA is considered as an example: the first recovered product can be the recovered PHA in a “raw” state. The second product can be PHA-biopolymer pellets that are safely distributed and stored. The PHA-biopolymer pellets can be regarded as the final product if it is purchased by, for example, a researcher to do a reference product analysis. In most cases, these biopolymer pellets will be used by industries to produce final products such as disposable tableware or food packaging materials. The quality specifications are then defined by requirements set for the production of the final product. The specifications are often set by a specific industry. The same condition is also applied for metal recovery.

When the recovered resources and the final products are produced by the same actor, a clear division between the recovered resource quality and the final product quality might be less necessary. This is because the responsible actor can design the production facility as such according to the composition of their recovered resources. However, industries generally prefer to have a consistent product quality. In a case when one centralized production facility uses recovered resources from different WWTPs, the standardized quality for the recovered resources will become more crucial.

To summarize, the responsible actors in resource recovery are encouraged to gather information from different regulations and different sources to validate the quality of the products, as outlined in Table 2.

3.2 Human health protection

Pillar-2 is dedicated to human health protection. The goal is to move from a mere end-product quality control to a comprehensive risk evaluation. The risk evaluation focuses on identifying and mitigating the health risk from the use of wastewater recovered products.

The flow scheme for establishing a monitoring plan to control human health risk is outlined in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Flow scheme for establishing monitoring plan for health protection

To ensure human health protection, the Pillar-2 assessment favours and demands an understanding of the system components from the production process to the end consumers. To guarantee a comprehensive assessment in all supply chains, QMRA and QCRA methods will be used. QMRA and QCRA assessments start with identifying hazards and exposure scenarios as their problem formulation step. These steps are adopted in the flow scheme, Figure 5.

Depending on the identified hazards and relevant exposure scenarios in each recovery case, some of the microbiology and chemical parameters for the health risk assessment may already be included in the monitoring plan for Pillar-1. Yet, this might not be the case. Even if some pathogens and toxic pollutants are regulated, the maximum limit set in the regulations may not adequately cover relevant risks to protect human health and the environment (Dingemans et al., 2020)

Due to the nature of current EU regulation objectives which is to facilitate the circular economy transition (European Commission, 2020a), it is important to challenge the hazard identification step using different regulations and health guidelines. This step is a prerequisite to ensure that problematic pollutants such as CECs, priority substances, and disinfectant by-products are not overlooked. Overview of regulations that can be relevant to be used as a starting point for hazard identification is listed in Figure 5.

Figure 6: Main steps in health risk assessment

Next to this hazard identification step, communicating the identified hazards and their relevant exposure scenarios is necessary for checking the completeness of the initial monitoring parameter list. The consultation must involve authorities and representatives of relevant exposure groups. This communication step serves as a means to stimulate transparency and the inclusion of all affected actors in the decision-making process. The product of the communication step will be the list of agreed-communicated hazards and exposure scenarios that later is used to perform the health risk assessment.

Conducting a risk assessment is a procedure that is introduced more in resource recovery projects. For resource recovery actors that are not familiar with the chemical and microbial health risk assessment, the simplified main steps for performing health risk assessment are delineated in Figure 6. The required input information and expected output of the assessment are also indicated. The descriptions and equations used for the quantitative health risk assessment are discussed in more detail in Chapter 4.

3.3 Environmental protection

Implementing the circular economy concept in wastewater resource recovery involves the risk of introducing hazardous substances to enter or re-enter into the environment (Bodar et al., 2018). The risk of persistent, bio-accumulative, and toxic substances staying in the circular loop must be prevented at all costs. In this framework, the flow scheme will help to identify relevant harmful substances and their exposure pathways specifically for unregulated substances such as contaminants of emerging concerns (CECs).

Figure 7: Flow scheme for establishing monitoring plan for environmental protection

Generally, product quality specifications do not include parameters for environmental hazards. In this case, Pillar-3 can be used as a proactive risk measure. For ensuring a comprehensive environmental risk assessment, QCRA method is used. In QCRA, the assessment starts with the identification of hazards and exposure pathways in its problem formulation step. These steps are adopted in the flow scheme in Figure 7.

For monitoring parameters, depending on the identified hazards and relevant exposure scenarios, some of the contaminants may already be included in the monitoring plan for Pillar-1. If this is not the case, the important monitoring parameters and monitoring points can still be captured and included in the monitoring plan by using the QCRA problem formulation principle.

Figure 8: Main steps in environmental risk assessment

If the concerned environmental endpoints are known, the referred regulation in Figure 7 can be used to identify the required monitoring parameters accordingly. For instance, the monitoring parameters can be based on the EU Water Framework Directive; EQS Directive and recent CECs watch-list (European Commission, 2000, 2013, 2020b) when the affected endpoints involves surface water.

In typical regulatory frameworks, environmental risks are often expressed by ratios between the predicted environmental concentration (PEC) and the reference value Predicted-No Effect Concentrations (PNEC) for the targeted environmental endpoints or ecosystem (ECHA, 2016a). The PEC values are estimated from environmental exposure assessment step. When the PEC exceeds the reference value (PNEC), thus the ratio PEC/PNEC exceeds 1, the risk is unacceptable and risk control measures are considered necessary. If the ratio is below 1 the risk is considered acceptable. The detailed steps for conducting the environmental risk assessment are outlined in Figure 8 and described in section 4.2.2.2.

The H2020 P-Rex project (Kraus & Seis, 2015) can be used as an example of the environmental risk assessment. In P-Rex project the authors considered three exposure scenarios:

1. Hazard application – soil – plants – humans by plant consumption
2. Hazard application – soil – soil organisms
3. Hazard application – soil – groundwater

The identified exposure pathways for fertilisers can be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Exposure pathways for fertilizers risk assessment (Kraus & Seis, 2015)

In fertilizer risk assessment, the study often shows an overlap of health risks and environmental risks. In such cases critical endpoints in the assessment must be defined. The exposure scenario-1 concerns health risk with human endpoint and with two midpoints (accumulation of hazard in topsoil and accumulation of hazard in an edible part of the plant due to plant uptake). The exposure scenarios-2 and 3 are related to environmental risk with soil organisms and groundwater as the endpoints. The exposure scenario-3 includes the soil compartment as the midpoint. In this case, the migration or leaching of the hazard in the soil has to be modelled as well.

To manage the challenges of defining the appropriate exposure scenarios/pathways, consultation with relevant environmental authorities is included in the flow scheme, Figure 7. This activity serves as a second control to ensure a comprehensive assessment. Similar as in Pillar-2, the result of this consultation step will be the list of agreed-communicated hazards and exposure scenarios, that later is used in the environmental risk assessment.

Example of the monitoring plan developed using the 3-pillar evaluation principle is presented in Appendix I. The example concerns the demonstration case in Norway: Biopellet Soil Improver.

4 Assessment methods for quality and risk analysis

Deliverable 2.1 focuses on the assessment of product quality, health risks and environmental risks. The selected assessment tools for analysing the recovered products are:

1. Product quality assessment according to EU regulations, relevant guidelines, and similar products in the market
2. Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) is used to assess health risks due to microbial pathogens
3. Quantitative Chemical Risk Assessment (QCRA) is used to assess health and environmental risks due to hazardous chemicals

4.1 Product quality assessment

In the product quality assessment, the evaluation is performed by comparing the composition of the recovered products with EU regulations or similar conventional products in the market. The required data (model input) and the expected results (model output) of the product quality assessment are summarized below:

Model input:

- Measured composition of the recovered products at the sampling point
- EU regulation for a particular recovered product or a proposed benchmark from a similar conventional product in the market

Model output:

- Compliance or non-compliance
- Frequency of non-compliance and the magnitude of deviated values

The product can be marketed when the quality specifications are fulfilled. Otherwise, there should be an improvement in the recovery and/or production process. Another option is to consider a different application for the recovered product that requires lower quality specifications.

4.2 Risk assessment

Risk assessment can be applied to various fields and endpoints ranging from technical and economic risks to human health and environmental risks. Regardless of the application fields, risk assessment will always comprise four main activities which are hazard identification, hazard characterization, exposure assessment, and risk characterization (Danish EPA, 2013; Ren & Zhang, 2019; WHO, 2010, 2016).

For health and environmental risk assessments, these four main steps are elaborated as the followings:

1. Hazard Identification

Hazard identification is the problem formulation part of the risk assessment where the pathogens and hazardous chemicals which could potentially harm people and the environment are identified. In this initial step, hazards are only identified, not quantified.

Defining the exposure scenarios is also part of the hazard identification. The information from exposure scenarios is important for estimating the exposure dose in the exposure assessment step.

2. Hazard characterization

The main task in hazard characterization is the information inventory and determination of the properties of a chemical or microbial hazard. For microbial risk, a functional relation is derived between the number of organisms ingested and the probability of infection. This is the so-called dose-response relationship which links the estimated exposure dose to the probability of infection or illness (WHO, 2016).

For chemicals, tolerable concentrations or no-effect concentrations are derived from toxicological testing. Distinctions are made between health (human endpoint) and environmental endpoints. For human health, the guidelines to indicate a safe dose are denoted as Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI) and Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI). Whereas for environmental endpoints, the guideline values are usually expressed as Predicted No-Effect Concentrations (PNECs) for different environmental compartments (Seis & Remy, 2013; WHO, 2010).

3. Exposure assessment

Exposure assessment aims at quantifying the magnitude and frequency of exposure to chemicals and pathogens. The identified exposure pathway(s) or exposure scenarios contain essential information to estimate the intake dose or the Predicted Environmental Concentration (PEC).

4. Risk characterization

Risk characterization puts together the collected information during hazard assessment and the predicted exposure dose or concentration in step-3 to formulate an estimation of the type, magnitude, and probability of the present risk. The purpose of the risk characterization is to provide a quantitative statement about the estimated exposure dose relative to its most appropriate guideline value (ECHA, 2016a; WHO, 2010, 2016).

The risk assessment by US EPA and WHO is based on the tiered principle. Depending on the purpose and scope of the assessment, a risk assessment can be conducted in a simple approach based on readily available data and conservative assumptions (US EPA, 2021b; WHO, 2016). If a very basic assessment does not generate adequate information to support decision-making, a more detailed or refined assessment can be conducted.

4.2.1 Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment

QMRA is used to estimate the probability of infection or illness when a population is exposed to pathogens. Hence, the endpoint of interest is human health. The required data and the expected results for QMRA are listed below:

Model input:

- Measured reference pathogens or indicator pathogens in the recovered products at the point of use
- Default input values such as parameters for dose-response model, inadvertently ingested volume, inhalation rate collected from internationally accepted guidelines such as WHO and US EPA.

Model output:

- Risk of illness is quantified in terms of its additional Disability Adjusted Life Years per person per years (DALYs pppy)

The four main steps of QMRA are explained below (WHO, 2016):

1. Hazard identification

In the general framework for developing the monitoring plan, the hazard identification of pathogens and their exposure scenarios are already incorporated in the Pillar-2 flow scheme in Figure 5. Thus, during the operation of the pilot study, the concentration of these targeted pollutants will be measured and collected.

2. Hazard characterization

In this step, the health impact data for the identified pathogens and the specific study population are compiled. The collected information includes the type of health effects, the severity and duration of a disease or illness that may occur after ingestion of the pathogen and available information on the relationship between ingested dose and the probability that adverse health effects (infection, illness, sequelae) occur (dose-response relationship). Also, the fraction and vulnerability of the population exposed may also have to be considered.

In hazard characterization, the dose-response model is an important quantitative element for the risk estimate. It provides the critical link between pathogen exposure and computed health outcomes (WHO, 2016). Given a known dose of the pathogen (D), dose-response models, which are generated based on clinical trial data, are used to estimate the probability of response e.g., infection or illness data. The Beta-Poisson and exponential functions are widely used to model the dose-response relationships. The equation for beta-Poisson and exponential functions are given below, respectively (Ren & Zhang, 2019):

$$P_{response} = P_{inf,daily} = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{D}{\beta}\right)^{-\alpha} = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{D}{N_{50}} \left(2^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} - 1\right)\right)^{-\alpha} \tag{1}$$

$$P_{response} = P_{inf,daily} = 1 - e^{(-k \cdot D)} \tag{2}$$

Where D is the estimated exposure dose of pathogens per exposure event. In the exponential models, k represents a pathogen survival probability of reaching and infecting a host given that a certain dose is ingested or inhaled. In the Beta-Poisson models, N_{50} represents the dose at which 50% of the population is expected to be affected and α is the slope parameter to model pathogen survival probabilities. The information about the best-fit parameters k , α and β (or, N_{50}) in dose-response models can be obtained from databases such as QMRA Wiki from the Centre for Advancing Microbial Risk Assessment⁵ or WHO QMRA guidelines (WHO, 2016).

3. Exposure assessment

This step aims to determine the frequency and magnitude of exposure to pathogens via the identified exposure pathways and during hazardous events defined in the problem formulation (WHO, 2016).

⁵ Available at: <http://qmrawiki.org/content/recommended-best-fit-parameters>, accessed in 16.10.2021

The estimated exposure dose includes voluntary consumption (e.g., drinking water, food crops) and involuntary consumption (e.g., accidental ingestion, aerosol ingestion/inhalation, dermal contact). Examples of formulas for calculating exposure dosage are given below:

- Exposure dose through inadvertently ingested liquid (WHO, 2016):

$$D (oral) = C_{pathogen} \cdot V/1000 \quad (3)$$

- Exposure dose through inhalation e.g., legionella (Hamilton & Haas, 2016):

$$D (inh) = C_{pathogen} \cdot IR \cdot L_{aer} \cdot ET \quad (4)$$

Where $C_{pathogen}$ is the pathogen concentration in bulk water (number of pathogens/L), V is the volume of inadvertently ingested liquid (mL), IR is inhalation rate (m^3/m in), L_{aer} is the load of aqueous aerosols of respirable diameter in air (L/m^3), ET is exposure time (min), and D is the estimated pathogen dose (number of pathogens).

Exposure Assessment calculation and Tools by inhalation⁶, ingestion⁷ and dermal⁸ can also be downloaded from US EPA web page (US EPA, 2021a).

4. Risk characterization

The risk may be quantified in different exposure groups, including the probability of infection, probability of illness, expected number of illness cases and measures for burden of disease, such as disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). DALYs is the metric used in WHO guidelines to compare different disease outcomes.

There are two approaches to defining tolerable health consequences:

1. Based on the frequency of a particular disease occurring, which is measured directly as infection cases per person per year (pppy),
2. By incorporating disease severity to calculate disability-adjusted life years (DALY) per person per year.

The equations for combining multiple exposure events, estimating illness probability and illness severity are given below (Ren & Zhang, 2019; WHO, 2016).

$$P_{inf,ann} = 1 - (1 - P_{inf,daily})^N \quad (5)$$

$$P_{ill,ann} = P_{inf,ann} \times P_{ill|inf} \quad (6)$$

$$DB_{ill,ann} = P_{ill,ann} \times DB_{case} \times S_f \quad (7)$$

Where $P_{inf,daily}$ is the probability of infection as a result of a single exposure event, or in this case daily, $P_{inf,ann}$ is the probability of infection as a result of multiple exposure events or annually, N is the number of exposure events, $P_{ill|inf}$ is illness-to-infection ratio, $P_{ill,ann}$ is the probability of illness per year, DB_{case} is the disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) per illness case caused by a certain pathogen, S_f is the susceptibility fraction of the population, and $DB_{ill,ann}$ is annual disease burden.

⁶ Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/expobox/exposure-assessment-tools-routes-inhalation>

⁷ Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/expobox/exposure-assessment-tools-routes-ingestion>

⁸ Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/expobox/exposure-assessment-tools-routes-dermal>

The US EPA uses risk benchmark of $\leq 10^{-4}$ infection cases per person per year (pppy), while the WHO risk benchmark is when the annual disease burden $\leq 10^{-6}$ DALYs pppy. In this report we propose to use the WHO tolerable risk benchmark which is 10^{-6} DALYs pppy as a reference.

Example

Reference case adapted from WHO QMRA guidelines, Table A6.1 (WHO, 2016) and WHO guidelines: Safe use of wastewater, volume 2 (WHO & UNEP, 2006a).

1. Hazard identification (Problem formulation)

How do we formulate the problem?

The purpose of the QMRA is to set the required Rotavirus reduction in a water reclamation facility.

The scope of the QMRA is defined by:

Identified pathogens: The assessment is undertaken specifically for Rotavirus.

Pathogen source : The pathogen source is the WWTP effluent. Rotavirus in WWTP effluent is reported to be 50 genomic copies/L.

Exposure scenarios :

- Exposure route through accidental ingestion of irrigation water via leafy vegetables consumed raw.
- Exposure group is consumers. It is assumed that all population are susceptible to diarrhoea, $S_f = 1$.
- Typically, 10 mL of irrigation water remains on 100 g leafy vegetables.
- Average consumption is 100 g leafy vegetable per person every second day throughout the year.

Health outcome : Annual probability of diarrheal illness.

2. Hazard characterization

Collected data for the assessment:

- WHO health-based target is 1×10^{-6} DALY pppy.
- Disease burden due to rotavirus is 1.4×10^{-2} DALYs per illness case.
- Dose-response model for Rotavirus infection is characterized using a beta-Poisson model with parameters: α 0.253 and N_{50} 6.17
- Illness to infection ratio for Rotavirus is 0.05. This is low because most of salad consumers are usually above the age of three and their immunity is already developed.

3. Exposure assessment

Number of hazardous events throughout the year (N) is 365/2.

$$\text{Tolerable } P_{inf,ann} = \frac{1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ DALY pppy}}{1.4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ DALYs per illness case} \cdot 1 \cdot 0.05 \text{ illness/infection}}$$

$$\text{Tolerable } P_{inf,ann} = 1.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ infections per person per year}$$

$$P_{inf,daily} = 1 - (1 - P_{inf,daily})^{1/N} = 1 - (1 - 1.4 \times 10^{-3})^{1/\left(\frac{365}{2}\right)} = 7.7 \times 10^{-6}$$

Using equation 1 to calculate the tolerable exposure dose (D):

$$P_{inf,daily} = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{D}{\beta}\right)^{-\alpha} = 1 - \left(1 + \frac{D}{N_{50}} \left(2^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} - 1\right)\right)^{-\alpha}$$

$$\text{Tolerable } D = \frac{[1 - P_{inf,daily}]^{-1/\alpha}}{N_{50} / (2^{1/\alpha} - 1)} = \frac{[1 - 7.7 \times 10^{-6}]^{-1/0.253}}{6.17 / (2^{1/0.253} - 1)} = 7.1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ per day}$$

4. Risk characterization

What are the conclusions from the results?

A dose of 7.1×10^{-5} rotavirus is contained in the remaining 10 mL on the vegetable leaves at the time of consumption. This is equal to a rotavirus concentration of 7.1×10^{-3} per litre. The number of rotaviruses in the WWTP effluent is 50 genomic copies/L. Hence, the required pathogen Log Reduction Value (LRV) is:

$$LRV = \log_{10}(50) - \log_{10}(7.1 \times 10^{-3}) = 4$$

The required rotavirus reduction is 4 LRV. In this example it is assumed that there is 1 LRV between last irrigation and the consumption due to washing. Taking this 1 LRV into account, the water reclamation facility has to achieve a 3 LRV. In this example, additional UV disinfectant of 40 mJ/cm^2 will be adequate to provide additional 3 LRV (WHO, 2017).

Verification monitoring:

The 3 LRV by treatment is verified by the reduction in the number of a pathogen indicator organism, not by measuring rotavirus numbers in samples of WWTP effluent and reclamation plant effluent. *Escherichia coli* is recommended for this purpose. Yet, thermotolerant coliforms can also be used. WHO has a recommendation for *E. coli* verification numbers per 100 mL for various reduction of viral, bacterial and protozoan pathogens (WHO & UNEP, 2006a).

4.2.2 Quantitative Chemical Risk Assessment

Hazardous chemicals can cause adverse impacts on both human health and the environment. Chemical risk assessment is used to define the probability of chemical agents exceeding predefined environmental thresholds or health-based precautionary values. The scope of chemical risk assessment ranges from local exposure assessments, for specific sites, to regional exposure assessment, for example, regarding a registration of new chemicals (ECHA, 2016c). The endpoints of interest in QCRA are human health and the environment.

Model input:

- Measured chemical hazardous substances in the recovered products at the point of use
- Default values for daily intake, tolerable/acceptable daily intake (TDI/ADI), predicted environmental concentration (PEC) and predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC) from internationally accepted guidelines

Model output:

- Risk is expressed in terms of risk characterisation ratio (RCR) or risk quotient (RQ) for each environmental endpoint, by comparing the estimated exposure/intake to the tolerable or acceptable effect concentrations (ADI, PNECs).

In this chapter the four main steps for assessing chemical risk for both human health and the environment are elaborated.

4.2.2.1 Chemical-based health risk assessment

The four key steps in chemical-based health risk assessment (Ren & Zhang, 2019; WHO, 2010) are described below:

1. Hazard identification

In the general framework for developing the monitoring plan, the hazard identification of toxic chemicals is already incorporated in the health risk control flow scheme in Figure 5. Thus, during the operational of the pilot study, the concentration of these targeted pollutants will be measured and collected. Data on chemical hazards can be obtained from databases from ECHA⁹, WHO/IPCS¹⁰, US-EPA¹¹, OECD¹², and EFSA¹³ and in the opinions from the EU Scientific Committees.

2. Hazard characterization

In hazard characterization, the information of tolerable level of exposures is collected. Basically, the task is to find out how large doses it takes to get poisoned by a chemical. The information for characterization usually consists of a no-observed-adverse-effect level (NOAEL), no-observed-effect level (NOEL) or cancer potency factor, and the application of uncertainty factors to account for interspecies and intraspecies variability, data quality and other uncertainties. This information is used to develop guidance values, such as the TDI and ADI (WHO, 2010).

TDI/ADI are used to state a safe daily dose or a safe concentration, which is usually given in mg/kg body weight or in mg/m³ for gas/inhalable chemicals. Depending on which authority is consulted, the acceptable chemical dose may be denoted differently as outlined in Table 3 (Danish EPA, 2013; Environmental Health Australia (EHA), 2012; WHO, 2010).

For the harmonization of the health assessment, the health-based dose concept using TDI/ADI, will be used to indicate the calculation example.

⁹ Available at: <https://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>

¹⁰ Available at: <http://www.who.int/ipcs/en/>

¹¹ Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/risk/human-health-risk-models-and-tools>

¹² Available at: <http://webnet.oecd.org/hpv/ui/Search.aspx>

¹³ Available at: <http://www.efsa.europa.eu/>

Table 3: Different concepts of health-based doses

Concept	Authoritative body	Definition
Tolerable daily intake (TDI)	WHO, EFSA	An estimate of the daily intake of a substance that can occur over a lifetime without appreciable health risk. It may have different units depending on the route of administration. The term 'tolerable daily intake' is used when the chemical is a potential food or environmental contaminant. While exposure should not occur, a TDI is an established health limit below which lifetime exposure should not have any adverse health effects.
Acceptable daily intake (ADI)	WHO, EFSA	An estimate of the daily intake of a substance that can occur over a lifetime without appreciable health risk. <i>Without appreciable risk</i> means the adverse effects will not result even after a lifetime of exposure. ADI is expressed in milligrams per kilogram of body weight per day (mg/kg/day). The term 'acceptable daily intake' is used for chemicals such as pesticides (herbicides, insecticides, and antifungals) that are deliberately used on food crops or food-producing animals and for which residues may be expected to occur in food.
Reference dose (RfD)	US-EPA	An estimate (with uncertainty factors) of the daily exposure (mg/kg/day) to the general human population (including sensitive sub-groups) that is likely to be without an appreciable risk of deleterious effects during a lifetime of exposure. It is derived from the NOAEL or the LOAEL by application of uncertainty factors that reflect various types of data used to estimate RfD and an additional modifying factor, which is based on professional judgement of the entire database of the chemical. The RfD is equivalent in meaning to tolerable daily intake (TDI) and acceptable daily intake (ADI).
Acute reference dose (acute RfD)	US-EPA	An estimate of substance that can be ingested in a period of 24 hours or less per unit body weight without appreciable health risk to the consumer.
Derived no effect level (DNEL)	ECHA	DNEL represents the level of exposure above which humans should not be exposed. DNELs are derived for substances based on: Population (workers, consumers, and the general population), route (inhalation, dermal and ingestion exposure) and duration (acute and long-term exposure).
Derived minimal effect level (DMEL)	ECHA	DMEL expresses an exposure level corresponding to a low, possibly theoretical, risk, which could be seen as a tolerable risk. It is usually used to

		represent different lifetime cancer risks, e.g., a risk for cancer in 1 per 100.000 exposed (10^{-5}) or 1.000.000 exposed individuals (10^{-6}).
Benchmark dose (BMD)	WHO, EFSA, US-EPA	An estimate of substance derived from studies in which experimental animal are given daily doses that produce a predefined cancer incidence e.g., 5% or 10%
Benchmark dose level (BMDL)	WHO, EFSA, US-EPA	A lower one-sided confidence limit on the BMD.
Minimal risk level (MRL)	ATSDR in USA	An estimate of the daily human exposure to a hazardous substance that is likely to be without appreciable risk of adverse non-cancer health effects over a specified duration of exposure.
Threshold of toxicological concern (TTC)	ILSI, EFSA, US-FDA, EMA	A level of exposure for all chemicals below which there would be no appreciable risk to human health.

3. Exposure assessment

Before human exposure to a chemical substance in the recovered products can take place, the substance must be able to migrate out, to leach or be liberated from the products. The magnitude of the migration depends on the properties of the recovered products, and the chemical and physical properties of the chemical pollutants. A migration estimate may be made from knowledge of similar cases with similar matrices or substances, and in some circumstances the migration can be measured or calculated.

Direct human exposure to chemical pollutants can take place through three routes of exposure (ECHA, 2016b):

- Ingestion or oral
- Inhalation
- dermal

Information about reference data for estimating exposure dose can be found in the US EPA Exposure Factors Handbook (US EPA, 2011). The principles in calculations of exposure are illustrated by some formulas below (ECHA, 2016b).

Ingestion/oral exposure

For the oral exposure scenario, the oral dose of toxic chemical in the inadvertently ingested product is given by:

- For solid products e.g., sewage sludge, soil improver or cellulose (ECHA, 2016b)

$$D (oral) = \frac{Q_{prod} \cdot F_{ch} \cdot n \cdot 1000}{BW} \quad (8)$$

- For liquid products e.g., reclaimed water or liquid fertilizers (ECHA, 2016b)

$$D (oral) = \frac{V_{prod} \cdot C_{ch} \cdot n}{BW \cdot 1000} \quad (9)$$

Where Q_{prod} is the amount of ingested product (g), F_{ch} is the mass fraction of the toxic chemical in the product (g/g of product), V_{prod} is the volume of ingested product (mL), C_{ch} is the concentration of the toxic chemical in the liquid product (mg/L), n is the number of

events per day (d^{-1}), BW is average body weight (kg), and D is the exposure dose or intake dose of chemical per body weight per day ($mg/kg_{bw}/d$).

- Example of a calculation formula for exposure through the pathway of ingestion contaminated crops (Ren & Zhang, 2019)

$$D (oral) = \frac{C_{pollutant} \cdot TF \cdot D_{food\ intake}}{BW} \quad (10)$$

Where $C_{pollutant}$ is the pollutant concentration in soil (mg/kg), TF is the transfer fraction from soil-to-plants or plant uptake, and $D_{food\ intake}$ is the average daily intake of the contaminated crops (kg/d).

Here 100% migration or leaching of the chemical substance from the material to human organ tissue is assumed as a starting point.

Dermal exposure

For the dermal exposure scenario, the dermal dose is given by:

$$D (derm) = \frac{L_{derm} \cdot A_{skin} \cdot n}{BW} \quad (11)$$

Where L_{derm} is the expected dermal load in the skin due to migration (mg/cm^2) and A_{skin} is contact area between product and skin (cm^2).

In this equation the default rate of 100% dermal absorption is assumed. This estimate can be further refined if data is available for the substance in relation to the absorption rate.

Inhalation exposure

For the inhalation exposure scenario, the concentration of toxic chemical in the air and the inhaled dose are given by:

$$C_{inh} = \frac{Q_{prod} \cdot F_{ch} \cdot 1000}{V_{room}} \quad (12)$$

$$D (inh) = \frac{F_{resp} \cdot C_{inh} \cdot I_{H_{air}} \cdot T_{contact}}{BW} \cdot N \quad (13)$$

Where V_{room} is the size of the room, default is $20\ m^3$ (m^3), C_{inh} is the aerosolised chemical concentration in the room (mg/m^3), F_{resp} is the respirable fraction of the inhaled chemical (m^3), $I_{H_{air}}$ is human inhalation rate (m^3/d), $T_{contact}$ is the duration of contact per event, default is 1 day (d), and N is the average numbers of events per day (d^{-1}).

4. Risk characterization

In quantitative chemical risk assessment, risk is expressed by comparing estimated exposure from step-3 to the tolerable/acceptable effect levels/concentrations (TDI, ADI). The risk outcomes are expressed by the RCR (Risk Characterization Ratio) or sometimes also referred to as RQ (Risk Quotient) or HQ (Hazard Quotient). For consistency in the report, the term RCR is used, and the formula is given by:

$$RCR = \frac{\text{estimated daily intake dose}}{TDI} \quad (14)$$

Typically, characterisation ratios (RCR) are calculated for each single endpoint. The RCR values are interpreted as follows (ECHA, 2016a):

If $RCR < 1$ → it means that the health risk is adequately controlled. Thus, the intended product application is acceptable.

If $RCR \geq 1$ → it means that the health risk is not controlled. The intended product application is not acceptable.

A $RCR > 1$ implies a toxicological concern for the exposure. The severity of this depends on the nature of the effect that is the basis for the hazard characterization and the magnitude of which the value of 1 is exceeded.

Aggregate risk

It is possible to combine RCR to account for multiple scenarios, for example due to exposure of the same type of chemical via different route, or exposure for several chemicals on the same type of health effect.

For example, the sum of inhalation, dermal and oral RCRs each based on tolerable dosage on liver effects:

$$RCR_{total} = RCR_{inh} + RCR_{derm} + RCR_{oral} \quad (15)$$

Or, for example the sum of RCRs for substance A, B and C based on tolerable dosage on anti-androgenic effects:

$$RCR_{total} = RCR_{substance A} + RCR_{substance B} + RCR_{substance C} \quad (16)$$

Detailed understanding and careful attention must be given when these risks are aggregated. The following guidelines from U.S. EPA¹⁴ and OECD¹⁵ can be used to assist this type of assessment.

4.2.2 Chemical-based environmental risk assessment

The objective of the environmental hazard assessment is to classify the substance regarding intrinsic hazardous properties for the environment, and to determine a predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC) below which adverse effects in a certain environmental compartment are not expected to occur.

1. Hazard identification

In the general framework for developing the Monitoring plan, the hazard identification of toxic chemicals is incorporated in the environmental risk control flow scheme in Figure 7. In addition to this, the information on relevant substance properties (physical-chemical, fate as well as (eco)toxicological properties) and mapping of uses should also be collected in this step. Mapping of uses consists of identifying all the uses of the substance including realistic information on the corresponding conditions of use. During the pilot study, the concentration of these targeted pollutants will be monitored and measured.

¹⁴ Available at:

<https://www.epa.gov/expobox/exposure-assessment-tools-tiers-and-types-aggregate-and-cumulative#input>

¹⁵ OECD (2018), Considerations for Assessing the Risks of Combined Exposure to Multiple Chemicals, Series on Testing and Assessment No. 296, Environment, Health and Safety Division, Environment Directorate.

2. Hazard characterization

Hazard characterization consists of obtaining the appropriate guidance values for the predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC) for the environmental compartments that are considered to be affected by the identified hazardous chemicals.

3. Exposure assessment

The purpose of the exposure assessment is to quantitatively define a dose or concentration that can be used to estimate risk. The estimated environmental exposure levels can be expressed as the Predicted Environmental Concentration (PEC).

To calculate the PEC, the information on the conditions of use and the related estimation of release to air, soil, surface water and groundwater during the whole life span of the product is needed. Information on the fate and distribution of the released chemical in the different environmental compartment such as air, soil/sediment, surface water, groundwater, and biota are also needed.

4. Risk characterization

Risk characterisation combines the results of hazard identification and exposure assessment. It basically consists of obtaining the appropriate health-based guidance values and comparing these with exposure assessment data. For consistency in the report, the term RCR is used, and the formula is given by:

$$RCR = PEC/PNEC \quad (17)$$

RCR values are interpreted as follows:

- If $RCR < 1$ → the environmental risk is acceptable
- If $RCR \geq 1$ → the environmental risk is not acceptable

Summary of available tools and information for conducting Environmental risk assessment can be found in OECD web page¹⁶.

Guidance on how to perform Environmental exposure assessment can be based on the ECHA Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment (ECHA, 2016c).

Examples of environmental and health risk assessment for water reuse, fertilizer and sewage sludge case studies are available in:

1. Demonstration study by DEMOWARE project (2013)
2. Quantification of potential hazards resulting from agricultural use of the manufactured fertilizers by Kraus & Seis (2015)
3. Risk assessment of contaminants in sewage sludge applied on Norwegian soils by Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food Safety, VKM (Eriksen et al., 2009)

Option for Deterministic or Probabilistic methods

In risk assessment, quantification can be made using deterministic or probabilistic methods. In probabilistic method, often using Monte Carlo simulations, all the possible outcomes from the risk results are captured. Thus, the output will be a large set of results

¹⁶ Available at : <https://www.oecd.org/env/ehs/summarytableofavailabletoolsforriskassessment.htm>

rather than a single number. While in deterministic methods, point estimates is determined based on average exposure or realistic worst-case exposure.

Since the use conditions often vary among consumers, average exposures will often underestimate the exposure for a large part of the population considered. A realistic worst-case exposure is normally supposed to cover 95% of the population. If a point estimate representing a worst-case exposure seems unrealistically high, such an estimate may be subject to further refinement by using probabilistic methods for reducing the uncertainty and variability in the results (WHO, 2016).

Most of QCRA analysis are performed using a deterministic method. A new probabilistic procedure to perform QCRA proposed by (Cantoni et al., 2021) can also be used as a reference case on how to perform a probabilistic chemical risk assessment, to estimate health based values from other data such as Drinking water regulation and to estimate human equivalent dose based on mice toxicology studies (interspecies toxicokinetic).

4.2.3 Databases

Conducting a risk assessment involves an extensive data inventory. In this section, overview of risk assessment tools and databases that can be used to retrieve relevant information is listed:

1. Chemical database from ECHA and WHO/IPCS

ECHA, the European Chemicals Agency is an independent regulatory agency driving the implementation of the REACH legislation. The ECHA has classification and labelling information on notified and registered chemical substances, available at the following link: <https://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>

IPCS, the International Programme on Chemical Safety is a cooperative programme between WHO and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). They have databases on chemicals and internationally peer-reviewed chemical safety-related documents that can be accessed at: <https://inchem.org/#/>

2. Risk assessment tools and database from US EPA

US EPA has developed risk assessment tools (online models and spreadsheets), and guidance documents for assessing and managing health and environmental risks. Renowned database such as ECOTOX and ECOSAR predictive model are also listed in the web page. The links are available below:

<https://www.epa.gov/risk/human-health-risk-models-and-tools>

<https://www.epa.gov/risk/ecological-risk-models-and-tools>

3. Risk Assessment Tools, guidelines, and database from OECD

Summary of available risk assessment tools, guidelines and suggested databases from OECD are available at:

<https://www.oecd.org/env/ehs/summarytableofavailabletoolsforriskassessment.htm>

Within the Wider Uptake project, a database is developed and made available for public. The results from monitoring plans for product quality, health risks and environmental risks will be stored on the platform. The platform can be used to demonstrate the safety of water reuse products and data transparency to public consumers.

5 References

- Bodar, C., Spijker, J., Lijzen, J., Loop, S. W. Der, Luit, R., Heugens, E., Janssen, M., Wassenaar, P., & Traas, T. (2018). *Risk management of hazardous substances in a circular economy*. 212, 108–114.
- Cantoni, B., Penserini, L., Vries, D., Dingemans, M. M. L., Bokkers, B. G. H., Turolla, A., Smets, P. W. M. H., & Antonelli, M. (2021). Development of a quantitative chemical risk assessment (QCRA) procedure for contaminants of emerging concern in drinking water supply. *Water Research*, 194, 116911. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2021.116911>
- Danish EPA. (2013). *Guidance for risk assessment of chemicals in consumer articles and products* (Issue 125). <http://www2.mst.dk/Udgiv/publications/2014/03/978-87-93178-21-2.pdf>
- DEMOWARE project. (2013). D3.2 *Show case of the environmental benefits and risk assessment of reuse schemes* (Vol. 1). <http://demoware.ctm.com.es/en/results/deliverables>
- DG Environment. (2021). *Bio-based, biodegradable, and compostable plastics*. https://ec.europa.eu/environment/topics/plastics/bio-based-biodegradable-and-compostable-plastics_en#ecl-inpage-832
- Dingemans, M. M. L., Smets, P. W. M. H., Medema, G., Frijns, J., Raat, K. J., van Wezel, A. P., & Bartholomew, R. P. (2020). Responsible water reuse needs an interdisciplinary approach to balance risks and benefits. *Water (Switzerland)*, 12(5), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/W12051264>
- ECHA. (2016a). Guidance on Information Requirements and Chemical Safety Assessment - Part E: Risk Characterisation. In *European Chemicals Agency* (Issue May).
- ECHA. (2016b). *Guidance on Information Requirements and Chemical Safety Assessment Chapter R.15: Consumer exposure assessment* (Issue May).
- ECHA. (2016c). *Guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment Chapter R.16: Environmental exposure assessment* (Issue February).
- Environmental Health Australia (EHA). (2012). *Environmental Health Risk Management - Guidelines*.
- Eriksen, G. S., Amundsen, C. E., Bernhoft, A., Eggen, T., Grave, K., Halling-Sørensen, B., Källqvist, T., Sogn, T., & Sverdrup, L. (2009). Risk assessment of contaminants in sewage sludge applied on Norwegian soils. In *Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food Safety (VKM)*.
- European Biochar Foundation (EBC). (2016). Guidelines for a Sustainable Production of Biochar. *European Biochar Foundation* (EBC), April, 1–22.
- European Biogas Association. (2021). *Overview on key EU policies for the biogas sector*. <https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/overview-on-key-eu-policies-for-the-biogas-sector/#>
- European Bioplastics e.V. (2016). *What regulatory framework is there for bioplastics on EU-level and what initiatives are underway? – European Bioplastics e.V.* <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/faq-items/what-regulatory-framework-is-there-for-bioplastics-on-eu-level-and-what-initiatives-are-underway/>

- European Commission. (2000). Directive 2000/60/EC, EU Water Framework Directive (WFD). *Official Journal of the European Communities*, L 327/1-L 327/72.
- European Commission. (2008). Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste. *Official Journal of the European Union*, 3–30. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781782258674.0028>
- European Commission. (2013). Directive 2013/39/EU, (revised) Environmental Quality Standards Directive (EQSD), List Priority Substances. *Official Journal of the European Union*, August, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781782258674.0032>
- European Commission. (2018a). Directive (EU) 2018/2001, *Renewable Energy Directive II (RED II)*. December. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2018.328.01.0082.01.ENG&toc=OJ:L:2018:328:TOC
- European Commission. (2018b). Directive 2018/851 amending Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste Framework. *Official Journal of the European Union*, 1907, (L-150/109-140). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018L0851>
- European Commission. (2019). *Regulation (EU) 2019/1009, EU fertilising products: Rules on the Making Available on the Market of EU Fertilising Products and Amending Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 and Repealing Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003*. 1–114. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/1009/oj>
- European Commission. (2020a). *Circular economy action plan. European Commission*, March, 28. <https://doi.org/10.2775/855540>
- European Commission. (2020b). Decision (EU) 2020/1161, Watch-List of emerging pollutants. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 257, L 257/32-L 257/35. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2020.257.01.0032.01.ENG&toc=OJ:L:2020:257:TOC
- European Commission. (2021). *Proposal for amending Renewable Energy Directive, COM/2021/557 final*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52021PC0557>
- Hamilton, K. A., & Haas, C. N. (2016). Critical review of mathematical approaches for quantitative microbial risk assessment (QMRA) of: Legionella in engineered water systems: Research gaps and a new framework. *Environmental Science: Water Research and Technology*, 2(4), 599–613. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6ew00023a>
- Huygens, D., Saveyn, H. G. M., Tonini, D., Eder, P., & Delgado Sancho, L. (2019). Technical proposals for selected new fertilising materials under the Fertilising Products Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2019/1009) - Process and quality criteria, and assessment of environmental and market impacts for precipitated phosphate salts & derivate. In Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2760/186684>
- Kehrein, P., Van Loosdrecht, M., Osseweijer, P., Garfí, M., Dewulf, J., & Posada, J. (2020). A critical review of resource recovery from municipal wastewater treatment plants- market supply potentials, technologies, and bottlenecks. Royal Society of Chemistry. *Environmental Science: Water Research and Technology*, 6(4), 877–910. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ew00905a>
- Kraus, F., & Seis, W. (2015). *Sustainable sewage sludge management fostering phosphorus recovery and energy efficiency*.
- Ren, H., & Zhang, X. (2019). High-risk pollutants in wastewater. In *High-Risk Pollutants in Wastewater*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2018-0-00194-2>

- RIVM. (2019). *Creating Safe and Sustainable Material Loops in a Circular Economy*.
<https://doi.org/10.21945/RIVM-2018-0173>
- Seis, W., & Rem y, C. (2013). *D3. 1 Appropriate and user-friendly methodologies for Risk assessment, Life Cycle Assessment, and Water Footprinting* (Vol. 1, Issue 619040).
<http://demoware.ctm.com.es/en/results/deliverables>
- US EPA. (2011). *Exposure Factors Handbook 2011 Edition (Final Report)*. U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, Washington, DC, EPA/600/R-09/052F (Issue September).
<https://cfpub.epa.gov/ncea/risk/recordisplay.cfm?deid=236252>
- US EPA. (2021a). *Exposure Assessment Tools by Routes*.
<https://www.epa.gov/expobox/exposure-assessment-tools-routes>
- US EPA. (2021b). *Exposure Assessment Tools by Tiers and Types - Screening-Level and Refined* / US EPA. <https://www.epa.gov/expobox/exposure-assessment-tools-tiers-and-types-screening-level-and-refined>
- WHO/IPCS. (2004). *Risk Assessment Terminology*. *Chemistry International -- Newsmagazine for IUPAC*, 23(2). <https://doi.org/10.1515/ci.2001.23.2.34>
- WHO. (2010). WHO human health risk assessment toolkit : chemical hazards. *IPCS Harmonization Project Document*, xv, 87 p.
- WHO. (2016). Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment: Application for Water Safety Management. *WHO Press*, 187. <http://www.who.int>
- WHO. (2017). *WHO Guidelines for drinking-water quality* (4th ed.).
<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241549950>
- WHO, & UNEP. (2006a). Safe use of wastewater, excreta, and greywater guidelines. Volume 2: Wastewater use in agriculture. *In WHO: Vol. II*.
http://whqlibdoc.who.int/publications/2006/9241546832_eng.pdf
- WHO, & UNEP. (2006b). Safe use of wastewater, excreta, and greywater guidelines. Volume 4: Excreta and greywater use in agriculture. *WHO, IV*, 204.
http://whqlibdoc.who.int/publications/2006/9241546832_eng.pdf

Appendix I: Example of Monitoring Plan

Biopellet Soil Improver

Pillar-1: Quality compliance

Responsible actor: WWTP/WRRF (IVAR)

Recovered resource: Digestate

Monitoring parameter	Maximum value	Unit	Monitoring frequency	Monitoring location	Reference
E. Coli (or, Enterococcaceae as option)	0	CFU	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
Salmonella spp.	0	CFU	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
Cadmium (Cd)	2	mg/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
Hexavalent Chromium (Cr VI)	2	mg/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
Mercury (Hg)	1	mg/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
Nickel (Ni)	50	mg/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
Lead (Pb)	120	mg/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
Arsenic (As), inorganic	40	mg/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
Copper (Cu)	300	mg/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)

D2.1 – Procedure for monitoring and control of health and quality risks

wider uptake

Zinc (Zn)	800	mg/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
Sum of PAH-16	6	mg/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, CMC 5
Macroscopic impurities >2 mm in any of the following forms: glass, metal, or plastics	2	g/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, CMC 5
Sum of macroscopic impurities	5	g/kg DM	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, CMC 5
Stability criteria:					
Oxygen uptake rate, or	25	mmol O ₂ /kg organic matter/h	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, CMC 5
Residual biogas potential	0.25	L biogas/g VS	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, CMC 5
Phosphonates*	0.5 %	wt.	monthly	Digestate	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009

* Phosphonates shall not be intentionally added to any EU fertilising product. Unintentional presence of phosphonates shall not exceed 0,5 % by mass.

Pillar-1: Quality compliance

Responsible actor: Production facility/Fertiliser factory (HØST)

Final product: Biopellet soil improver

Monitoring parameter	Minimal value	Unit	Monitoring frequency	Monitoring location	Reference
% material of which is of solely biological origin	95 %	wt.	one/product	Biopellets	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
% dry matter (DM)	20 %	wt.	one/product	Biopellets	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
% organic carbon (C org)	7.5 %	wt.	one/product	Biopellets	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)
%TP solubility in water	40 %	-	one/product	Biopellets	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, L*
%TP solubility in neutral ammonium citrate	75 %	-	one/product	Biopellets	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, L*
%TP solubility in formic acid (only for soft rock phosphate)	55 %	-	one/product	Biopellets	Reg.(EU) 2019-1009, L*
DM content		% wt.	one/product	Biopellets	Reg. (EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)L*
TN**		% wt.	one/product	Biopellets	Reg. (EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)L*
Total P ₂ O ₅ **		% wt.	one/product	Biopellets	Reg. (EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)L*
Total K ₂ O**		% wt.	one/product	Biopellets	Reg. (EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)L*
pH		-	one/product	Biopellets	Reg. (EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)L*

D2.1– Procedure for monitoring and control of health and quality risks

wider uptake

Conductivity		m S/m	one/product	Biopellets	Reg. (EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)L*
Organic carbon (C org)		% wt.	one/product	Biopellets	Reg. (EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)L*
Organic nitrogen (N org) description of origin		% wt.	one/product	Biopellets	Reg. (EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)L*
Ratio C org /TN		% wt.	one/product	Biopellets	Reg. (EU) 2019-1009, PFC 3(A)L*

*L = Labelling. The content shall be declared.

** The content shall be declared, if exceeding 0.5 % by mass.

Pillar-2: Health protection

Identified hazards: E. coli, Salmonella spp., heavy metals

Exposure scenarios: 1. Consumers of the agricultural products are exposed to heavy metals due to plant uptake. Increment of heavy metal concentration in the consumable part of the crops after biopellet application will be monitored.

2. Farmers are exposed to pathogens due to the microbial regrowth during distribution and storage

Exposure routes: 1. Accidental ingestion during handling and application of biopellets in the field

2. End-consumers are exposed to heavy metals due to consumption of agricultural crops

Affected systems: Storage system and application field

Exposure groups: Farmers and end-consumers of agricultural products

Responsible actor: Production facility/Fertiliser factory (HØST)

Monitoring parameter	Measured value	Unit	Monitoring frequency	Monitoring location	Reference
E. Coli	Measured values	CFU	weekly	Biopellets	Consultation report dd-mm-yy
Salmonella spp.		CFU	weekly	Biopellets	
Cadmium (Cd)		mg/kg of dry weight	per harvest	Edible part of the crops	
Hexavalent Chromium (Cr VI)		mg/kg of dry weight	per harvest	Edible part of the crops	
Mercury (Hg)		mg/kg of dry weight	per harvest	Edible part of the crops	
Nickel (Ni)		mg/kg of dry weight	per harvest	Edible part of the crops	
Lead (Pb)		mg/kg of dry weight	per harvest	Edible part of the crops	
Arsenic (As), inorganic		mg/kg of dry weight	per harvest	Edible part of the crops	
Copper (Cu)		mg/kg of dry weight	per harvest	Edible part of the crops	
Zinc (Zn)		mg/kg of dry weight	per harvest	Edible part of the crops	

Pillar-3: Environmental protection

Identified hazards: Heavy metals and list of Hazardous Organic Chemicals (HOCs) from Environmental authority*. The list of monitored HOCs is adjusted based on the site-specific HOCs occurrence in the WWTP/WRRF.

Exposure scenarios: 1. Accumulation of hazardous chemicals (heavy metals and HOCs) in agricultural soil
2. Indirect risk for freshwater ecosystems via runoff and leaching and indirect risk for HOC presence in edible part of the crops due to HOC accumulation in agricultural soil.

Exposure pathways: Fraction of the hazardous chemicals in the product that potentially accumulates in the soil and in the edible part of the plant due to the application of biopellets in agriculture. The migration and accumulation of chemical in soil can generate indirect risk for freshwater ecosystems via runoff and leaching.

Affected compartments: Topsoil layer and surface water

Endpoints: Soil microorganisms, agricultural plants

Responsible actor: Production facility/Fertiliser factory(HØST)

Monitoring parameter	Measured value	Unit	Monitoring frequency**	Monitoring location	Reference
Hexavalent Chromium (Cr VI)	Measured values	mg/kg of dry weight	monthly	topsoil, adjacent surface water	Consultation report dd-mm-yy
Mercury (Hg)		mg/kg of dry weight	monthly	topsoil, adjacent surface water	
Nickel (Ni)		mg/kg of dry weight	monthly	topsoil, adjacent surface water	
Lead (Pb)		mg/kg of dry weight	monthly	topsoil, adjacent surface water	
Arsenic (As), inorganic		mg/kg of dry weight	monthly	topsoil, adjacent surface water	
Copper (Cu)		mg/kg of dry weight	monthly	topsoil, adjacent surface water	
Zinc (Zn)		mg/kg of dry weight	monthly	topsoil, adjacent surface water	

* Available at: <https://www.miljodirektoratet.no/globalassets/publikasjoner/m1503/m1503.pdf>

** Adjusted with the application frequency of the biopellets

D2.1– Procedure for monitoring and control of health and quality risks

Monitoring parameter	Measured value	Unit	Monitoring frequency	Monitoring location	Reference
Diethylhexyl phthalate (DEHP)	Measured values	µg/kg of dry weight	monthly	Phase-1: digestate, biopellets, top soil Phase-2: crop edible part, surface water*	Consultation report dd-mm-yy
Perfluorinated octane sulfonate (PFOS)		µg/kg of dry weight	monthly		
Perfluorinated octanoic carboxylic acid (PFOA)		µg/kg of dry weight	monthly		
Galaxolide (HHCB)		µg/kg of dry weight	monthly		
Tonalide (AHTN)		µg/kg of dry weight	monthly		
Decabromo-diphenylether (BDE-209)		µg/kg of dry weight	monthly		
Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB7)		µg/kg of dry weight	monthly		
Nonylphenol + nonylphenol ethoxylates (NP + NPE)		µg/kg of dry weight	monthly		

* Phase-2 is related to the indirect risk from HOCs leaching and soil-plant interaction (plant uptake). Phase-2 is commenced when significant HOC concentration is found in the biopellets, and the HOC leaching test confirms the leaching tendency of the HOCs.

